

GAMES AND GAME MOMENTS IN LESSONS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

Umirbaeva Ulzada

Student of the Faculty of Primary Education
Nukus State Pedagogical Institute

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ABSTRACT

The didactic game is a valuable means of nurturing the mental activity of children; it arouses in students a keen interest in the process of cognition. In it, children willingly overcome significant difficulties, train their strengths, develop abilities and skills. It helps to make any educational material exciting, evokes deep satisfaction in students, creates a joyful work mood, and facilitates the process of acquiring knowledge.

INTRODUCTION

Education in primary school is the foundation on which all further human activity will be built. It is important to teach a child of primary school age to master, transform and use large amounts of information in practical activities in a short period of time [1, p. 39]. The use of computers has become quite accessible in recent years. Therefore, the introduction of computer technologies in education can be considered a necessary step in the education system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The combination of traditional teaching methods and modern information and computer technologies contributes to this. After all, using a computer in the classroom allows you to make the learning process mobile and individual. The computer serves as a means for the child to develop new practical knowledge and skills.

The rapid development of new information technologies has left a definite imprint on the personality development of the modern child. A powerful flow of new information, advertising, the use of computer technology in television, the spread of electronic toys and computers have a great influence on the upbringing of a child and his perception of the world around him. The nature of his favorite practical activity - games - also changes significantly, and his favorite heroes and hobbies also change.

The game is a simple and close way for people to understand the surrounding reality; it is characterized by the most natural and accessible way to mastering certain knowledge, abilities, and skills. The game is a unique phenomenon of universal human culture. In no other type of activity does a person demonstrate such self-forgetfulness as in a game. That is why the game expands its principles, invading previously unpredictable areas of human life.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The didactic game is a valuable means of nurturing the mental activity of children; it arouses in students a keen interest in the process of cognition. In it, children willingly overcome significant difficulties, train their strengths, develop abilities and skills. It helps to make any educational material exciting, evokes deep satisfaction in students, creates a joyful work mood, and facilitates the process of acquiring knowledge.

What are the benefits of computer games and why they cannot be replaced simply by story-based games. Any child's fantasies, characters from books and fairy tales come to life on the display screen. But the objects of the surrounding world, numbers and letters also come to life. When they get into a computer game, they create a special world, similar to the real world, but also different from it [2, p. 89–93].

A child can control objects appearing on the computer screen, can make them change, appear or disappear, i.e. he feels their reality, as well as the reality of the things around him. At the same time, he cannot take them in his hands, cannot touch them. In addition, computer games are designed so that the child can imagine a single concept or a specific situation, but get a general idea of all similar situations or objects.

Thus, children develop such important thinking operations as generalization and classification. Computer classes contribute to the development of children's logical thinking. It is equally important that in these games the child begins to understand that the objects on the screen are not real things. In various games, these signs or symbols of real objects become more complex, become more and more generalized and look less and less like the surrounding real objects. Consequently, children very early begin to develop an understanding that there are several levels of reality in the world around us, these are real objects, and pictures, diagrams, these are words and equations, etc. Finally, these are our thoughts, which are the most complex ideal level of reality. They cannot be seen or touched, although they are as real as the truck in front of the child or the letters written on the screen.

Computer games are of great importance not only for the development of intelligence, but also for the development of their motor skills, more precisely, for the formation of motor coordination and coordination of joint activities of visual and motor analysis torov.

The child's desire to play, or as psychologists say "game motivation," helps the child acquire the knowledge that computer games carry. The child gradually begins to be interested in their content, and not just in the new and unusual form. Game motivation naturally turns into educational motivation, in the interest in the content of the task, an interest that underlies the formation of such important structures as cognitive motivation, voluntary memory and attention.

There are different types of computer gaming programs. So, for example, programs aimed at developing perception. These are very common programs in which you need to assemble a picture from several parts. The tasks can be varied according to the degree of difficulty, since the picture is divided into 8, 12, 16, 24, 48 parts. Since in many cases the work process involves counting the time and points accumulated by the players, this kind of program can be given to children not only in individual, but also in collective classes. form of a game - competition [3, p. 48–51].

You should draw the children's attention to the original picture, which must be carefully examined and remembered, since without this it is not possible to assemble it from its parts.

This is how we form in our children the foundations of voluntary memorization and attention necessary for normal mental development.

As part of drawing lessons, you can suggest using a variety of programs in which, using the cursor, you can draw any figure or even a picture. Such programs develop not only perception,

but also the imagination of children. The teacher himself can vary the tasks. Drawing with children or giving them the task to draw a picture of a certain content (for example, a warm sunny day or a cold winter evening).

Design programs are also of great importance for the development of children, in the process of which children need to either put together a figure of a certain shape from different pieces, or, on the contrary, divide an existing figure into given parts. These programs develop not only perception and coordination, but also children's imaginative thinking.

In addition to general educational game programs, there are also special programs for teaching children mathematics, Russian language, and logic. The value of these programs is that they present the content of these subjects in a more visual form, which allows children to easily and quickly master this material.

CONCLUSION

Modern information technologies give students access to non-traditional sources of information, increase the efficiency of independent work, provide completely new opportunities for creativity, acquisition and strengthening various skills allows for the implementation of fundamentally new forms and methods of training. The teacher receives additional opportunities to support and guide the student's personality, creative search and organization of their joint work.

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